

Heart and Vessels

PREDICTORS OF PERSISTENT PULMONARY HYPERTENSION AFTER MITRAL VALVE REPLACEMENT

--Manuscript Draft--

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Funding Information:	
Abstract:	<p>Background Persistent pulmonary hypertension (P-PH) after mitral valve replacement (MVR) leads to an increased risk of morbidity and mortality. We sought to determine which factors were involved in its occurrence.</p> <p>Methods Patients undergoing MVR for a three-year period were collected in a retrospective way. We excluded those with an available follow up shorter than 3 months. Sample size was 111 patients. PH was diagnosed if systolic pulmonary artery pressure (sPAP) estimated by Doppler-echocardiography was >40 mmHg. Clinical, echocardiographic and surgical factors were analysed.</p> <p>Results P-PH was present in 42,3% of patients after 12.6 months of mean follow up. P-PH was more frequently observed in elderly and female patients, in those with severe degrees of PH before surgery, and significant tricuspid regurgitation (TR). On multivariable analysis, significant TR (OR: 1.739; p=0.01) and more severe degrees of PH before surgery (OR: 1.761; p=0.03) were significantly associated with the presence of P-PH</p>

	<p>after MVR. Surgical factors related to P-PH were prosthesis size and tricuspid annuloplasty: no need for the performing of tricuspid annuloplasty (OR: 0.345; p=0.025) and the implantation of a smaller prosthesis (OR: 0.656; p=0.004) were related to higher rates of P-PH after MVR.</p> <p>Conclusion</p> <p>MVR was associated with high prevalence of P-PH after mid term follow up. Both PH and significant TR before surgery were associated with P-PH. Our data point out that MVR should be planned before the development of PH and greater TR. Smaller prosthetic size is also a risk factor for P-PH and bigger prostheses are desirable when possible.</p>
<p>Response to Reviewers:</p>	<p>Dear Editors,</p> <p>First of all I would like to thank the time your Editorial Office have spent considering our work and we also want to thank the chance you are giving us, by encouraging resubmission. You taking into consideration our resubmission is a really honour. Furthermore we appreciate all the comments coming from your Editorial office. I hope that the next lines can clarify point by point all the items:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •All the changes made in the final version resubmitted (included the new cites), are highlighted in red font colour. •As you suggest, many articles published in the recent years in “Heart And Vessels” are relevant and address an issue related to ours. We think that the addition of the next cites makes the discussion of our work, stronger: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> oAmano H, Toyoda S, Arikawa T, Inami S, Otani N, Nishi Y, Kitagawa Y, Taguchi I, Abe S, Inoue T (2013) Left ventricular function in pulmonary hypertension. Heart Vessels 28:505-509. (New reference, number 27) oKaneko H, Suzuki S, Uejima T, Kano H, Matsuno S, Otsuka T, Takai H, Oikawa Y, Yajima J, Koike A, Nagashima K, Kirigaya H, Sagara K, Tanabe H, Sawada H, Aizawa T, Yamashita T (2014) Prevalence and the long-term prognosis of functional mitral regurgitation in Japanese patients with symptomatic heart failure. Heart Vessels 29:801-807. (New reference, number 28) oAoyagi S, Fukunaga S, Arinaga K, Tomoeda H, Akasu K, Ueda T (2010) Heart valve surgery in octogenarians: operative and long-term results. Heart Vessels 25:522-528. (New reference, number 33). <p>RESPONSE TO THE REVIEWERS</p> <p>On behalf of all the authors I want to thank the reviewers for the comments made. We hope the next explanations will be able to answer your questions about our paper.</p> <p>Response to Reviewer 1:</p> <p>I totally agree with your concern about the statistical analysis. The paragraph included in “Material and Methods” (placed in page 6 and 7), is a generic report of the analysis done. I recognise that the lack of a deep description regarding the variables included in the regression model, can lead to misunderstanding. In the multivariable model we had to choose among the 9 variables that were significant after univariable analysis. These 9 variables were: age, gender, BSA, mean gradient of the native valve, preoperative sPAP categorized, mean sPAP, TR severity ≥ 3, tricuspid annuloplasty, and size of mitral prosthesis. We decided to include those with smaller p values (sPAP categorized, TR ≥ 3 and tricuspid annuloplasty). We excluded mean sPAP because of redundancy. Among the other variables, were selected those more clinically relevant such as age, gender and BSA. The final multivariable model consisted of 6 variables. We agree with you that the rule of 1 variable, every 10 outcomes must be followed when possible, but we also agree with you in the generic character of it. Because of this we decided not to remove any other variable and adjust the model to 6 variables, pretty close to the ideal number. If you consider absolutely necessary to adjust the model in 5 variables, please let us know. In order to clarify the way the statistical analysis was done I have modified the explanation in the paragraph of page 6 and 7 (red text in the final version).</p> <p>Only one regression model was performed. The results are divided into preoperative factors and surgical factors, to make the report more easy to follow and not because two regression models were done.</p> <p>We also coincide with you that the inclusion of the mitral PPM in the multivariable model (clustering together the "meaning" of BSA and size of mitral prosthesis) would have been the solution for this. As we report in the paragraph of limitations our work has been made retrospectively and we did not have this variable available. Most of the</p>

echocardiograms were performed in an era in which PPM was not so relevant, the measurement was not routinely made and was also not digitally recorded.

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- At the end of page 4 "Final sample size included was 111 patients" has been modified. The word "included" has been removed.
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RESPONSE TO THE REVIEWERS

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PREDICTORS OF PERSISTENT PULMONARY HYPERTENSION AFTER MITRAL VALVE REPLACEMENT

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All of the authors take responsibility for all aspects of the reliability and freedom from
bias of the data presented and their discussed interpretation.

None of the authors declare any potential conflict of interest.

ABSTRACT

Background

Persistent pulmonary hypertension (P-PH) after mitral valve replacement (MVR) leads to an increased risk of morbidity and mortality. We sought to determine which factors were involved in its occurrence.

Methods

Patients undergoing MVR for a three-year period were collected in a retrospective way. We excluded those with an available follow up shorter than 3 months. Sample size was 111 patients. PH was diagnosed if systolic pulmonary artery pressure (sPAP) estimated by Doppler-echocardiography was >40 mmHg. Clinical, echocardiographic and surgical factors were analysed.

Results

P-PH was present in 42,3% of patients after 12.6 months of mean follow up. P-PH was more frequently observed in elderly and female patients, in those with severe degrees of PH before surgery, and significant tricuspid regurgitation (TR). On multivariable analysis, significant TR (OR: 1.739; p=0.01) and more severe degrees of PH before surgery (OR: 1.761; p=0.03) were significantly associated with the presence of P-PH after MVR. Surgical factors related to P-PH were prosthesis size and tricuspid annuloplasty: no need for the performing of tricuspid annuloplasty (OR: 0.345; p=0.025) and the implantation of a smaller prosthesis (OR: 0.656; p=0.004) were related to higher rates of P-PH after MVR.

Conclusion

MVR was associated with high prevalence of P-PH after mid term follow up. Both PH and significant TR before surgery were associated with P-PH. Our data point out that MVR should be planned before the development of PH and greater TR. Smaller

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prosthetic size is also a risk factor for P-PH and bigger prostheses are desirable when possible.

Keywords: persistent pulmonary hypertension, mitral valve replacement, tricuspid regurgitation, and prosthetics size.

INTRODUCTION

1
2 Pulmonary hypertension (PH) is one of the most important risk factors for poor
3
4 outcomes after prosthetic mitral valve replacement (MVR). Severe PH is associated
5
6 with high-risk perioperative mortality [1,2] and also with increase in long-term
7
8 mortality. [3] Furthermore mild degrees of PH are related with significantly worse
9
10 exercise capacity after MVR and higher rates of morbidity and mortality. [4,5]
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14 In many patients, pulmonary arterial pressure descends soon after the surgery. The rapid
15
16 fall in left atrial (LA) pressure leads to a decrease in the passive component of PH. The
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18 subsequent progressive lowering in pulmonary pressures, occurring up to several
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20 months after the implant, is due to decreasing in pulmonary arterial vasoconstriction.
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23 However, the hypertrophy in the arteriolar medium layer, once established, does not
24
25 reverse, and this facilitates the appearance of residual or recurrent PH. [6,7]
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29 The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of pulmonary arterial
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31 hypertension after mitral valve replacement and analyse the clinical, echocardiographic
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33 and surgical factors involved in the presence of persistent pulmonary hypertension (P-
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35 PH).
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MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Population

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41 We conducted a retrospective study including all patients undergoing implantation of a
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43 prosthetic valve in mitral position from January 2005 to December 2007. A clinical and
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45 echocardiographic follow up of longer than 3 months was required for inclusion. Three
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47 hundred patients were operated on during this period; 135 were referred from other
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49 cities and were therefore excluded due to lack of data. From the remaining sample, 35
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51 patients were excluded due to lack of follow up; 10 were lost and 9 patients died
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53 perioperatively. Final sample size was 111 patients.
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Data Source

Clinical data were collected immediately before surgery and when the last available echocardiogram was performed. Clinical variables were extracted from the electronic clinical records of our institution and operative parameters were obtained from the surgical database. All the echocardiograms had been previously recorded and stored in digital format, and the echocardiographic variables were obtained once two different investigators reviewed the studies. Follow-up time was the period elapsed between the date of surgery and the last echocardiogram available after the implant. Data from echocardiograms performed in the first three months of follow up were neglected. The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the ethics board of our institution.

Baseline Parameters

Clinical variables: age, gender, body surface area (BSA), atrial fibrillation (AF), etiology (rheumatic, degenerative, endocarditis, or functional mitral disease) and predominant mitral valvulopathy (stenosis, regurgitation or double lesion) were analysed.

Echocardiographic variables: systolic pulmonary artery pressure (sPAP) was calculated by adding the right ventricle-right atrial (RV-RA) pressure difference to an estimation of RA pressure (from the diameter and the degree of collapse of the inferior vena cava during inspiration). [8] PH was diagnosed in those cases with sPAP > 40 mmHg estimated by echocardiography; mean pulmonary pressure obtained with an invasive method was not available. [9] We considered mild PH if sPAP was between 41 and 50 mmHg; moderate PH if sPAP was between 51 and 69 mmHg and severe PH, if sPAP ≥ 70 mmHg.

Other echo parameters collected were: LA diameter by M-mode, left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) by Teichholz method or Simpson when needed; [10] mitral

1 valve area estimated by pressure half time (PHT) and by mean gradient in cases of
2 mitral stenosis, performed when the patient's heart rate was between 60 and 80 beats
3 per minute and obtaining the average of at least 3 measures; and the severity of mitral
4 regurgitation (MR), tricuspid regurgitation (TR) and aortic regurgitation (AR) graded
5 from 0 to 4. [11]
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10 **Surgical data**

11 All surgeries were performed by full median sternotomy with cardiopulmonary bypass.
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13 Cardiac arrest was obtained by antegrade cold blood cardioplegia. [12] The size and
14 type of prosthetic valves implanted, were recorded along with the need for concomitant
15 aortic or tricuspid intervention.
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24 **Echocardiographic Assessment in the Follow up**

25 Prosthetic parameters collected were: maximum and mean gradients and peak E wave
26 mitral inflow velocity. LA indexed volume, left ventricle diastolic and systolic
27 diameters (LVDD/LVSD) and LVEF were collected too. We also analysed peak E'
28 wave velocity in septal annulus by tissue Doppler imaging, sPAP and the severity of
29 MR and TR. Echocardiographic studies were performed with two devices (Vivid 7,
30 General Electrics; ATL HDI 5000, Phillips Medical Ultrasound).
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41 **Statistical Analysis**

42 All collected data were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis, via frequency
43 measurements (absolute frequencies and percentages) if the variables were qualitative,
44 and via means and standard deviations (SD) if quantitative. Univariate analysis of the
45 quantitative variables was undertaken using the Student *t* test when their distribution
46 was normal, and the Mann-Whitney *U* test when they were not. The qualitative
47 variables were analyzed using the χ^2 or the Fisher exact test when the conditions
48 required for the former test were not met. Logistic regression analysis was performed to
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1 determine predictors of P-PH for each known or potential risk factor. **One** multivariate
2 logistic regression analysis was performed to determine independent predictors of P-PH,
3 including significant and close to significant factors ($p < 0.10$) after univariate analysis.
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5 **To adjust the model to the minimum number of variables, we selected those with**
6 **smaller p values (sPAP categorized, TR ≥ 3 and tricuspid annuloplasty). Mean sPAP**
7 **was excluded because of redundancy. Among the other variables, were selected those**
8 **more clinically relevant such as age, gender and BSA so the final model was composed**
9 **by 6 factors.** The data are expressed as odds ratio (OR) and 95% confidence interval
10 (CI) and were computed from the binomial distribution by using the Statistical Package
11 for Social Sciences (version 20.0, SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL, USA). A p value of less than
12 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

26 RESULTS

29 1. Clinical and Echocardiographic Baseline Characteristics of the Population 30 (Table 1)

33 Average age was 68.7 years, 67.6% were women and AF was present in 78.9% of the
34 population. Most of the patients were in NYHA functional class III-IV (72.3%). The
35 most frequent etiologies were rheumatic and degenerative valvular disease (93.6%).
36 Mitral stenosis or mixed dysfunction, were present in 64% of cases. Regurgitations such
37 as MR ≥ 3 or TR ≥ 3 were present in 52.3% and 34.2% of the patients, respectively, and
38 PH before MVR was present in 64.9 % of the patients (8.1% severe PH). Most of the
39 patients were in NYHA functional class III-IV (72.3%). Patients suffering from PH
40 were older, had larger LA diameter, underwent surgery more frequently because of
41 mitral stenosis and their mean transvalvular gradient was higher. They were also more
42 frequently affected with moderate to severe TR.

59 2. Surgical data

1 Most of the mitral prostheses were mechanical (82.9%) and number 25 (54%).
2 Tricuspid annuloplasty was performed in 34.2% of the patients. Concomitant aortic
3 replacement was performed in 48 patients; most of them due to moderate or severe
4 aortic regurgitation (66.6%); and coronary bypass graft surgery was also performed in
5 11.7% of the whole population (Table 1).
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11 **3. Echocardiographic Data in Follow up**

12 **3.1. Change in sPAP after Surgery**

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17 The proportion of patients with PH was reduced from 64.9% to 43.2% after MVR. Mild
18 PH was present in 23 patients (20.7%), moderate in 23 patients (20.7%) and was
19 considered severe in only 2 patients (1.8%). The average decrease in sPAP after surgery
20 was 7.1 mmHg (± 12.8).
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28 **3.2. Prosthetic Parameters**

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31 At 12.6 months (± 10.5 SD) of mean follow up, the average maximum gradient was 13.1
32 mmHg, the average mean gradient was 5.1 mmHg, and average peak E wave mitral
33 velocity was 173.3 cm/s.
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40 **4. Predictors of P-PH (Table 2)**

41 **4.1 Clinical and Echocardiographic Predictive Factors**

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44 On univariate analysis, the prevalence of P-PH was higher in older patients ($p=0.047$),
45 in women ($p=0.047$) and in those with less BSA ($p=0.048$). Furthermore, severe degrees
46 of PH ($p=0.015$) and TR ($p=0.002$) before surgery were found in the patients with P-
47 PH. Otherwise, patients with mitral stenosis and higher mean gradients showed a
48 greater prevalence of P-PH in the follow up ($p=0.033$).
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1 On multivariable regression analysis, only sPAP (categorized in degrees) (OR: 1.761;
2 95% CI: 1.053-2.943; p=0.03) and significant TR (≥ 3) (OR: 1.739; 95% CI: 1.133-
3 2.670; p=0.01) were found to be independent related to the presence of P-PH.
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6 **4.2 Surgical Factors Associated With P-PH**

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9 Smaller prostheses were implanted in women (p<0.001) and in patients with lower BSA
10 (p=0.013). Tricuspid annuloplasty (p=0.014), as well as a small-sized prosthesis
11 (p=0.048), were associated with P-PH as determined by univariate analysis and also by
12 multivariable analysis. Tricuspid annuloplasty (OR: 0.345; 95% CI: 0.136-0.873;
13 p=0.025) and prosthesis size (OR: 0.656; 95% CI: 0.493-0.873; p=0.004) were
14 independently associated with P-PH during follow up. No relationship between the
15 gradients of the aortic prosthesis and the appearance of P-PH was found.
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26 **5. Echocardiographic Factors Related with P-PH in the Follow up (Table 3)**

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28 Higher maximum (p=0.011) and mean (p=0.044) transprosthetic gradients as well as
29 higher peak E wave velocity (p=0.03) were found in patients with P-PH. There were no
30 differences between left volumetric parameters or LVEF and the presence of P-PH in
31 the follow up.
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38 **DISCUSSION**

39 **Main Findings**

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41 We found a high percentage (up to 43%) of PH among patients undergoing mitral valve
42 replacement. Persistent PH after mitral valve replacement was independently associated
43 with the degree of PH and TR severity before surgery as well as the prosthesis size
44 implanted and the need for tricuspid repair.
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53 **Preoperative Factors**

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55 It is worth noting the high percentage of PH among patients undergoing mitral valve
56 replacement. In our registry, 64.9 % had sPAP > 40 mmHg and in 45% of the patients
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1 sPAP was > 50 mmHg. European and American guidelines include previous PH as an
2 indication for mitral surgery. European guidelines recommend surgery if sPAP > 50
3 mmHg at rest (IIa) or > 60 mmHg at exercise (IIb) [3] while in the American guidelines
4 both sPAP>50 mmHg at rest and sPAP>60 mmHg at exercise, represent a
5 recommendation IIa, except in patients with mitral stenosis favorable for valvuloplasty
6 in which sPAP> 50 mmHg is considered class I. [13] Both guidelines do not give
7 different values of sPAP based on the kind of surgery (repair vs. replacement); however
8 clinical practice seems to make this difference. In patients undergoing mitral repair the
9 prevalence of PH before surgery does not exceeded 35% [14-17] and in patients
10 undergoing percutaneous balloon valvuloplasty, PH prevalence before surgery does not
11 exceed 20% according to different large-scale international registries. [7,18-20]
12 Nevertheless, the prevalence of presurgical PH among patients undergoing mitral
13 replacement is over 65%. [4,21,22] Our data and all of these data above suggest that
14 clinicians are more reluctant to follow clinical guidelines when the surgery planned is
15 MVR and also show that class IIa indications are used in patients suitable for mitral
16 repair and not for mitral replacement.

17 Patients with persistent PH in our study are older, affected by more severe degrees of
18 presurgical PH and TR; and have also higher mean gradients when mitral stenosis. All
19 these data reflect a more severe and chronic left heart disease, which is associated with
20 higher incidence of pulmonary vascular disease. [23-28] The relationship between
21 presurgical PH and P-PH after MVR has been shown in many studies [4,22,29] and it is
22 also demonstrated in ours (Figure 1). A significant TR associated with mitral lesions is
23 generally the final result of long standing PH, which leads to the enlargement of right
24 cavities and tricuspid annulus. The severity of TR has already been associated with
25 higher prevalence of PH after surgery. [21,30,31]

1 Our findings allow us to formulate the hypothesis that these patients with pre-existing
2 PH who undergo MVR, and/or significant TR have already developed pulmonary
3 vascular disease with an irreversible component of PH. The heterogeneity of the study
4 population could explain why other factors such as ventricular dimensions were not
5 statically significant.
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10 **Surgical Factors**

11 P-PH was significantly associated with the implantation of a smaller prosthesis (Figure
12 2) and with the need for mitral and tricuspid combined surgery. In this regard, there are
13 several studies that have linked the so-called mitral "mismatch" with P-PH after
14 surgery. [4,21] This relative stenosis of the mitral prosthesis could have a direct impact
15 on trans-prosthetic gradients and therefore on the pressure in the LA and the passive
16 component of PH. This affects directly the pulmonary vasculature, contributing to
17 maintain the structural and functional changes, thereby keeping both the active and
18 passive components of the PH. The significant relationship between prosthetic gradient
19 and pulmonary pressure after surgery, in our study, confirms the importance of the
20 prosthetic hemodynamic in the presence of P-PH.
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38 The relationship between the need for tricuspid repair and P-PH is logical because
39 annuloplasty was performed in patients with significant TR, which was also associated
40 with P-PH. The performance of tricuspid annuloplasty, along with the replacement,
41 resulted in a protective factor for the development of P-PH in the follow-up. Delaying
42 the intervention not only exposes to higher risk of P-PH, but also leads the patient to a
43 significant TR, to a more complicated surgery with double intervention and the
44 possibility of right ventricle dysfunction.
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55 **Clinical Impact**

56 Mitral valve repair is the technique of choice and has many advantages over MVR. [3]
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1 In spite of this, an important percentage of patients are not suitable for repair. In current
2 guidelines, in the absence of a class I indication, is not clear the optimal time for
3 surgery regarding the type of procedure available to be performed. This may lead
4 clinicians to overlook the prognostic value of PH or TR in patients who are not suitable
5 for repair, causing surgery to be postponed until a class I indication presents.
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10 Our results show that the delay in surgery has adverse consequences. As we observed,
11 postponing the time of the intervention increases PH before surgery, with the possibility
12 of an irreversible component that will lead to P-PH. On the other hand, patients are
13 exposed to a higher surgical risk because surgical mortality increases as previous sPAP
14 increases (2%-3% rates of mortality with no PH or mild PH Vs. 8%-12% rates with
15 moderate to severe PH). [32,33]
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26 The delay of the surgery involves a greater number of cases with mitral and tricuspid
27 valve surgery. This implies not only a longer intervention time, but also makes more
28 probable operating a patient with major component of RV dysfunction.
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33 The clinical consequences of a delayed surgery can be even more important in patients
34 in whom it is foreseeable a small prosthesis to be implanted. In these cases a significant
35 mitral gradient would difficult the regression of PH.
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41 **Study Limitations.**

42 As a retrospective study some limitations like the absence of some predictors of interest
43 (prosthesis mismatch was not performed) occurred. Sample size, also limits the power
44 of our study. A mixture of etiologies has been used, and the population studied is not
45 homogeneous. PH was estimated using Doppler echocardiography and we do not have
46 invasive measurement of right heart pressures to correlate with our non-invasive
47 estimation of pulmonary pressure. As PH tends to regress after MVR, a longer follow-
48 up would have been necessary to confirm our results.
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CONCLUSION

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2 In a population with a high prevalence of preoperative PH, mitral valve replacement
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4 was associated with a high prevalence of P-PH after mid term follow up. Since the
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6 severity of previous PH and the size of the prosthesis implanted were strongly
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8 correlated with the persistence of PH after surgery, both factors should be considered in
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10 order to improve the results of MVR in the follow up. Surgery should be performed
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12 before the development of moderate to severe PH or significant TR, mainly in cases in
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14 which prosthesis mismatch is anticipated at the time of operation. An effort should be
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16 done to implant the bigger prosthesis when possible.
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FIGURE LEGENDS

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Figure 1. Relationship between sPAP before and after surgery

Figure 2. Relationship between postoperative sPAP and prosthesis size

Table 1. Baseline and perioperative characteristics of the whole population and according to the presence of PH before MVR

	Total (n=111)	No preoperative PH (n=39)	Preoperative PH (n=72)	p value
Age (years) (SD)	68.7 (9.4)	67.8 (10.1)	69.3 (9.0)	0.487
Female (%)	75 (67.6%)	61.5%	70.8%	0.318
BSA (m ²) (DE)	1.7 (0.1)	1.74 (0.2)	1.69 (0.1)	0.321
AF (%)	78.9%	72.7%	82.9%	0.461
NYHA FC III-IV	80 (72.3%)	29 (37%)	51 (63%)	0.649
Etiology, n (%)				0.646
• Degenerative	52 (46.8%)	19 (48.7%)	33 (45.8%)	
• Rheumatic	52 (46.8%)	19 (48.7%)	33 (45.8%)	
• Endocarditis	3 (2.7%)	1 (2.6%)	2 (2.8%)	
• Functional	4 (3.6%)	0 (0%)	4 (5.6%)	
Predominant mitral dysfunction				0.335
• Regurgitation	40 (36%)	17 (43.6%)	23 (31.9%)	
• Stenosis	44 (39.6%)	12 (30.8%)	32 (44.4%)	
• Mixed dysfunction	27 (24.4%)	10 (25.6%)	17 (23.6%)	
Mitral valve area (cm ²) (SD)*	1.2 (0.4)	1.3 (0.5)	1.2 (0.4)	0.903
Mean gradient (mmHg) (SD)*	11.7 (5.2)	11.3 (4.4)	11.9 (5.7)	0.673
MR severity ≥3	58 (52.3%)	20 (34.5%)	38 (65.5%)	0.880
TR severity ≥3	38 (34.2%)	3 (10.7%)	25 (89.3%)	0.002
Severe Aortic stenosis n (%)	16 (14.4%)	5 (31.2%)	11 (61.7%)	0.725
AR ≥ 3 **	32 (66.6%)	12 (31.6%)	20 (27.4%)	0.901
LVEF (%) (SD)	64.6 (9.9)	64.8 (10.8)	64.6 (9.4)	0.526
LA diameter	57.9 (13.2)	54.8 (13.6)	59.4 (12.8)	0.046
Mean sPAP (mmHg) (SD)	52.6 (13.9)	37.1 (3.1)	56.8 (13.9)	0.000
Degrees of sPAP, n (%)				0.000
• ≤40 mmHg	39 (35.1%)	39 (100%)	0 (0%)	
• 41-50 mmHg	22 (19.8%)	0 (0%)	22 (30.5%)	
• 51-69 mmHg	41 (36.9%)	0 (0%)	41 (56.9%)	
• ≥ 70 mmHg	9 (8.1%)	0 (0%)	9 (12.5%)	
Mitral Prosthesis n (%)				0.376
• Mechanical	92 (82.9%)	34 (87.2%)	58 (80.5%)	
• Biological	19 (17.1%)	5 (12.8%)	14 (19.5%)	
Prosthesis size, n (%)				0.574
• 23	2 (1.8%)	0 (0%)	2 (2.8%)	
• 25	60 (54%)	23 (59.0%)	37 (51.4%)	
• 27	31 (27.9%)	9 (23.1%)	22 (30.5%)	
• 29	15 (13.6%)	5 (12.8%)	10 (13.9%)	
• 31	3 (2.7%)	2 (5.1%)	1 (1.4%)	
Tricuspid annuloplasty	38 (34.2%)	9 (23.7%)	29 (76.3%)	0.068
Aortic prosthesis, n (%)	48 (43.2%)	18 (37.5%)	30 (62.5%)	0.649
Coronary by pass graft, n (%)	13 (11.7%)	7 (18.9%)	6 (9.5%)	0.222

AF: atrial fibrillation; AR: aortic regurgitation; BSA: body surface area; LA: left atrial; LVEF: left ventricular ejection fraction; MR: mitral regurgitation; NYHA FC: NYHA functional class; sPAP: systolic pulmonary arterial pressure; PH: pulmonary

hypertension; SD: standard deviation; TR: tricuspid regurgitation; *in patients with mitral stenosis; ** in the 48 patients who underwent aortic replacement.

Table 2. Baseline and perioperative characteristics according to the presence of persistent PH during follow-up

	No Persistent-PH (n=63)	Persistent-PH (n=48)	p value
Age (years) (SD)	67.2 (9.8)	70.8 (8.7)	0.047
Female gender (%)	60.3%	77.1%	0.047
BSA (m ²) (SD)	1.73 (0.2)	1.67 (0.2)	0.048
AF n (%)	21 (70%)	24 (88.9%)	0.081
NYHA Functional Class III-IV	45 (56.2%)	35 (46.8%)	0.929
Etiology, n (%)			0.473
• Degenerative	28 (44.4%)	24 (50.0%)	
• Rheumatic	29 (46.0%)	23 (47.9%)	
• Endocarditis	3 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	
• Functional	3 (4.8%)	1 (2.1%)	
Predominant mitral dysfunction			0.227
• Regurgitation	27 (42.8%)	13 (27.1%)	
• Stenosis	22 (34.9%)	22 (45.8%)	
• Mixed dysfunction	14 (22.2%)	13 (27.1%)	
Mitral valve area (cm ²) (SD)*	1.28 (0.5)	1.22 (0.3)	0.974
Mean gradient (mmHg) (SD)*	10.3 (4.2)	13.2 (5.9)	0.033
MR severity ≥3	35 (60.3%)	23 (39.7%)	0.425
TR severity ≥3	9 (32.1%)	19 (67.9%)	0.002
LVEF (%) (SD)	62.8 (10.6)	67.1 (8.3)	0.095
LA diameter	57.7 (13.1)	58.2 (13.4)	0.703
Mean sPAP (mmHg) (SD)	49.3 (12)	56.1 (15.1)	0.029
Degrees of sPAP before MVR, n (%)			0.015
• ≤ 40 mmHg	28 (44.4%)	10 (20.8%)	
• 41-50 mmHg	13 (20.1%)	10 (20.8%)	
• 51-69 mmHg	20 (31.7%)	21 (43.7%)	
• ≥ 70 mmHg	2 (3.2%)	7 (14.6%)	
Mitral Prosthesis n (%)			0.690
• Mechanical	53 (84.2%)	39 (81.2%)	
• Biological	10 (15.8%)	9 (18.8%)	
Prosthesis size, n (%)			0.048
• 23	0 (0%)	2 (4.2%)	
• 25	31 (49.2%)	27 (56.2%)	
• 27	16 (25.4%)	15 (31.2%)	
• 29	12 (19.0%)	3 (6.2%)	
• 31	3 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	
Tricuspid annuloplasty	15 (39.5%)	23 (60.5%)	0.008
Maximum gradient of the aortic prosthesis (mean mmHg)(SD) **	28.4 (10.7)	29.5 (10.1)	0.752

AF: atrial fibrillation; BSA: body surface area; LA: left atrial; LVEF: left ventricular ejection fraction; MR: mitral regurgitation; sPAP: systolic pulmonary arterial pressure; PH: pulmonary hypertension; SD: standard deviation; TR: tricuspid regurgitation; *in patients with mitral stenosis; ** in the 48 patients who underwent aortic replacement.

Table 3. Relationship between echocardiographic parameters and persistent PH after MVR

	No persistent PH (n=63)	Persistent PH (n=48)	p value
LA volume (ml/m ²) (SD)	88.3 (60.9)	70.7 (23.4)	0.779
LVDD (mm) (SD)	49.1 (10.2)	48.3 (7.4)	0.654
LVSD (mm) (SD)	32.6 (11.1)	31.3 (7.5)	0.845
LVEF (%) (SD)	61.9 (12.6)	64.1 (11.0)	0.880
E peak velocity (cm/s) (SD)	165.1 (32.8)	183 (42)	0.030
Maximum gradient (mmHg) (SD)	11.6 (4.1)	14.9 (6)	0.011
Mean gradient (mmHg)(SD)	4.6 (1.9)	5.5 (2.2)	0.044

LA: left atrial; LVDD/LVSD: left ventricular diastolic/systolic diameter; LVEF: left ventricular ejection fraction; PH: pulmonary hypertension; SD: standard deviation

Figure 1

[Click here to download Figure: Figure 1.jpg](#)

Figure 2

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